

Range-Free Positioning in NB-IoT Networks by Machine Learning: Beyond W_k NN

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Abstract—Existing proposals for positioning in narrowband Internet of Things (NB-IoT) networks based on range estimation are characterized by either low accuracy or lack of compliance with 3GPP standards. While range-free approaches taking advantage of machine learning (ML) have been recently proposed as a potential way forward, their evaluation has been carried out only in simulated environments, with the exception of weighted k nearest neighbors (W_k NN), recently tested on experimental data. This work investigates five ML strategies for range-free positioning in NB-IoT networks, based on W_k NN and its combination with preprocessing and classification algorithms as well as on artificial neural networks (ANNs). The strategies are evaluated on experimental data and are compared based on a set of key performance indicators measuring both positioning performance and processing load. Two different datasets taken at different times and locations were adopted, enabling the validation of strategies optimized on one testbed on the other, as well as the study of the impact of dataset features on performance. Results show that range-free positioning using ML is a viable solution in commercial NB-IoT networks, and that W_k NN and ANNs are at the two extremes in terms of a performance/complexity tradeoff; intermediate tradeoffs can be achieved by combining W_k NN with preprocessing techniques and classification models.

Index Terms—Machine learning (ML), narrowband Internet of Things (NB-IoT), positioning, weighted k nearest neighbors (W_k NN).

I. INTRODUCTION

NARROWBAND Internet of Things (NB-IoT), a standard defined by the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP), is arguably the most popular low power wide area network (LPWAN) technology, thanks to its low-cost and power-efficient

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design, specifically aimed to support IoT services [1]. NB-IoT was standardized by 3GPP in Release 13 [2], and is expected to maintain its prominent role as 5G and beyond-5G technologies are deployed, since no replacement technology has been defined in subsequent 3GPP releases [3]. As most IoT services either require or may benefit from location information [4], positioning in NB-IoT networks has become a major research topic, since the provision of position information by the NB-IoT radio interface would be beneficial under several points of view: first, it would enable the deployment of IoT tracking devices in GNSS-denied environments, such as large warehouses; second, it would allow deployment of location-aware services without the need for more expensive and energy-hungry global navigation satellite systems (GNSSs) chips since, even taking into account latest technology advances and the introduction of power saving management techniques, GNSS chips can take up to 10% of the power budget for an IoT device [5]. It is also worth observing that power saving management techniques for GNSS receivers typically operate by accepting worse positioning accuracy or availability in a tradeoff between efficiency and performance [5], indicating that achieving the typical GNSS accuracy of a few meters is often not a major concern in IoT applications characterized by low or no mobility. For this reason, 3GPP integrated in NB-IoT Release 14 positioning features borrowed from long term evolution (LTE), by introducing both an enhanced Cell ID uplink positioning scheme, taking advantage of timing, reference signal received quality (RSRQ), and reference signal received power (RSRP) measurements, and a downlink observed time difference of arrival (OTDOA) positioning scheme, supported by a dedicated narrowband positioning reference signal (NPRS) [6].

While the authors are not aware of any real world deployment of an NB-IoT-based positioning system based on either uplink Cell ID or downlink OTDOA, several studies investigated the performance of the latter scheme. In [7], a mathematical model was proposed to determine the probability of coverage by at least M eNBs, and the corresponding positioning performance as a function of M was analyzed, although no results on positioning accuracy were provided. Within 3GPP, multiple studies assessed the performance of OTDOA positioning, albeit only by simulation [8], [9], [10]; results showed a positioning error of 50 m with a probability of 0.89. A performance evaluation of the accuracy of 3GPP-OTDOA, based on simulations, was also presented in [11], showing an error of 76 m with a probability of 0.9 under favourable channel conditions. Several approaches to improve NB-IoT positioning accuracy using OTDOA were recently proposed. The use of successive interference cancellation (SIC) was explored in [12], with an increase from 56% to 86% of the percentage of devices located with an error below 500 m and an error below 200 m with probability 0.5. SIC was later adopted in combination with an adaptive scheme in [13], leading to an error below 50 m with probability 0.5. Frequency hopping over multiple resource blocks was proposed in [14], resulting in an error below 20 m with probability 0.5. A modified sequence for the generation of the NPRS signals was introduced in [15], leading to an error below 40 m with a 0.5 probability. Recently, the use of phase differences computed in the frequency domain was proposed in [16], leading to a root-mean-square error (RMSE) of the positioning error between 27.2 and 102.8 m depending on multipath conditions.

The above-mentioned proposals typically rely on features not defined in 3GPP standards and not available in a commercial user equipment: as a consequence, they were only tested by simulation. Early attempts to move from simulations to experimental evaluation were first reported in [17], where an NB-IoT system-on-chip (SoC) supporting OTDOA was introduced aiming at an error below 150 m. An SoC implementation of an NB-IoT receiver implementing OTDOA was presented in [18], and its accuracy was analyzed using synthetic signals from four cells, showing a RMSE of 48.5 m under standard coverage conditions for all cells, and of 68.5 m under extended coverage conditions for the weakest cell. More recently, in [19] experiments using a software radio implementation of an NB-IoT transceiver were carried out in a laboratory, emulating a NB-IoT deployment in an area of 1500×3000 meters covered by three NB-IoT base stations; an error below 150/200 m with probability 0.5 depending on channel conditions was reported, highlighting the difficulty to achieve satisfactory positioning accuracy with time-based methods in NB-IoT.

In the quest for higher positioning accuracy in NB-IoT networks, a parallel line of research emerged in the last few years, exploring range-free positioning techniques based on machine learning (ML) and power-related signal parameters, such as received signal strength indicator (RSSI), following a trend common to other LPWAN technologies, such as LoRaWAN and SigFox [20], [21]. The first and, as of today, most popular ML technique to be adopted was fingerprinting. In fingerprinting, the position of a target device is estimated by comparing signal parameters measured by the device from multiple transmitters

with parameters prerecorded from the same set of transmitters at known locations, referred to as reference points (RPs); the parameters measured at a given location define a unique *fingerprint* associated to the location. The position of the target device is typically obtained using the k nearest neighbors (k NN) [22] or weighted k NN (Wk NN) [23] algorithms, that sort RPs by decreasing similarity of their fingerprint to the one measured by the target device, and then compute a (weighted) average of the locations of the first k sorted RPs. Fingerprinting was widely investigated in the context of WiFi positioning, see [24] for a survey; in the following we will focus however on its use in NB-IoT networks.

Fingerprinting for NB-IoT was first introduced in [25], where Channel State Information data were used. The accuracy reported in [25] was very high, with an average positioning error of 1.2 m; the experimental setup included, however, the deployment of NB-IoT transmitters within the indoor environment, while commercial NB-IoT transmitters are typically deployed outdoors, at existing LTE sites. In addition, the data used in [25] to define signal patterns were based on amplitudes as received at multiple antennas for each receiver, a fairly complex setup compared to the capabilities of commercial NB-IoT devices. A more realistic example of fingerprinting in NB-IoT systems was presented in [26] and [27], where a fingerprint was defined by the RSSI of only one cell, i.e., the cell to which the NB-IoT device was connected, due to the hardware limitations of commercial NB-IoT modems used in the experiments. The limited amount of information defining each fingerprint led to a poor accuracy, with an average positioning error of about 180 m. More recently, fingerprinting using NB-IoT was investigated in [28] using RSRP data from multiple eNBs; development boards were used for data collection, in order to overcome the limitation of commercial NB-IoT devices. Improved positioning accuracy was obtained compared to [27], with an average positioning error of about 90 m. The authors of the present work investigated in [29] a Wk NN algorithm in combination with a set of new similarity metrics. The algorithm was tested on a large-scale experimental outdoor dataset for NB-IoT commercial networks collected by the authors in Oslo, Norway [30] using a Mobile Network Scanner, achieving an average positioning error below 20 m. The analysis was later extended in [31], where the positioning system included new data processing techniques as well as the combination of data from multiple operators. The performance evaluation was enhanced by introducing a second dataset collected in Rome, Italy, and showed an average positioning error of less than 15 m. Both datasets were made available under an open source license in [32] and [33] (a complete description of the data for the latter dataset is available in [34]). As of today, they remain the only large scale outdoor datasets available for NB-IoT; other datasets released under open source licenses were collected in indoor [35] or deep indoor [36] locations, and report data on a single PCI/network, making them very interesting for coverage studies but not suitable for work on positioning. An attempt to adopt an ML algorithm different from Wk NN, and in particular a feedforward neural network (NN), was presented in [37], but only evaluated by simulation. A worse performance than Wk NN was reported, with no quantitative indication of the average positioning error.

The above-mentioned brief survey indicates that ML-based for positioning in NB-IoT is still in its early stages, and the accuracy achieved in existing investigations is in most cases still rather low, with the exception of $WkNN$ using multiple cells. The complexity of $WkNN$ for a position estimation goes, however, as $O(Nd)$, where N is the number of RPs and d is the total number of signals detected in any of the N RPs, hindering its scalability to large areas and/or large numbers of targets. This observation motivated the study presented in [38], which aimed at investigating and comparing the performance of several ML-based positioning techniques, including $WkNN$, support vector machine (SVM), random forest (RF), and artificial NNs (ANNs), as well as their combinations, in an NB-IoT network. The present work extends [38] by introducing an additional strategy that relies on the combination of soft clustering and $WkNN$ and carrying out an exhaustive performance evaluation using the two large-scale experimental datasets previously described, enabling the assessment of the adaptability of the proposed strategies to different environments in the framework that includes both accuracy- and efficiency-related key performance indicators (KPIs) defined by revising those originally proposed in [38]. The contributions of this work can be summarized as follows.

- 1) It proposes novel positioning strategies based on combinations of $WkNN$, SVM, RF, and ANNs and of data preprocessing techniques aimed at reducing computational complexity.
- 2) It provides the first systematic performance analysis of ML-based positioning techniques for NB-IoT networks based on experimental data collected in two different cities in Europe.
- 3) It provides a quantitative comparison of the different strategies in terms of KPIs measuring both accuracy and computational complexity.

The rest of this article is organized as follows. Section II describes the data preprocessing algorithms and the ML techniques considered in this work, and introduces four positioning strategies; next, Section III describes the experimental data used in performance evaluation as well as the preprocessing technique applied to the Rome data. Section IV introduces the set of KPIs that are used for performance evaluation and presents and discusses the experimental results. Finally, Section V concludes this article.

II. ML STRATEGIES FOR RANGE-FREE POSITIONING

This study analyzes ML strategies that can be divided into two groups: a) $WkNN$ -based, combining $WkNN$ with preprocessing techniques and/or other ML algorithms aimed at reducing computational complexity; b) a strategy that does not adopt $WkNN$. The preprocessing techniques and ML algorithms are introduced in Sections II-A and II-B, respectively, followed by the definition of the proposed strategies in Section II-C.

A. Preprocessing Techniques

Preprocessing is a key step in the operation of a fingerprinting positioning system, and a wide range of preprocessing

techniques were proposed as part of the design of new positioning systems, in particular in the framework of indoor positioning based on WiFi; partially building on the classification proposed in a recent overview on positioning in WiFi systems [39], the following categories of preprocessing techniques can be identified.

- 1) Data cleansing and denoising, aiming at mitigating the impact of noise and artifacts in experimental data; this includes for example the replacement of missing entries with a default value [40], data smoothing [41], and the application of autoencoders to increase robustness to noise [42].
- 2) Feature tuning, including data scaling and normalization and outlier removal.
- 3) Feature extraction and dimensionality reduction in the feature space, based on techniques such as singular value decomposition, principal component analysis (PCA) as well as locally linear embedding, linear discriminant analysis, neighbor embedding, and autoencoding.
- 4) Dimensionality reduction in the point space, aiming at reducing the amount of data considered in each positioning attempt, most often by a clustering algorithm, either in its hard variant (a point is assigned to one and only one cluster) or in its soft one (a point can belong to all clusters at the same time, with different degrees of membership to each cluster). Clustering has been widely investigated in the context of indoor and outdoor positioning; extensive analyses comparing the positioning performance of fingerprinting systems adopting different hard clustering algorithms and similarity metrics were proposed in [43] and more recently in [44]. The latter work was extended in [45] by including both hard and soft clustering algorithms and by testing the performance of positioning systems on multiple wireless technologies.
- 5) Data augmentation, aiming at generating synthetic data starting from a small set of experimental data, with the goal of increasing positioning accuracy while limiting the effort for data collection. Techniques for data augmentation include, among others, spatial interpolation [46], [47], [48], [49], channel modeling [50], ML algorithms, such as regression and generative adversarial networks [51], and time interpolation across data screenshots [52].

In this work preprocessing techniques from most of the above-mentioned categories were adopted, the only exception being data augmentation. Data cleansing included the replacement of missing entries with a default value, as detailed in Section III-A, and the interpolation of feature values in the Rome dataset, as described in Section III-B, to compensate for artifacts in data collection; feature tuning techniques included data scaling and representation conversion, as described in Section IV-B. Dimensionality reduction in both feature and point space is however the main topic of interest in this work: rather than exploring a wide range for options for each class, we decided to select a few representative techniques for each of them and provide a first benchmark for complexity reduction, leaving the comparison across different preprocessing techniques for future work. PCA

was selected for reducing the number of signals d , while two different clustering algorithms were adopted for reducing the number of RPs N ; the techniques are briefly introduced in the following.

1) *PCA*: PCA is a well-known multivariate technique by which a set of l correlated variables $\{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_l\}$ is linearly transformed into a second set $\{z_1, z_2, \dots, z_l\}$ of uncorrelated variables characterized by the same overall variance of the original variables, referred to as principal components. The transformation is carried out by determining a particular orthonormal matrix \mathbf{U} such that $\mathbf{U}'\mathbf{S}\mathbf{U} = \mathbf{E}$, where \mathbf{S} is the covariance matrix for the original set of variables and \mathbf{E} is a diagonal matrix, with nonnull elements $\{e_{11}, \dots, e_{ll}\}$ corresponding to the eigenvalues of \mathbf{S} [53]. One key property of the PCA representation is that matrices \mathbf{S} and \mathbf{E} are characterized by the same trace, corresponding to the overall variance of the original variables; the eigenvalues in \mathbf{E} are thus direct indicators of the contribution of each variable to the overall variance. In many cases, a relatively small subset of the principal components contributes to most of the overall variance, suggesting that restricting the analysis to such subset might be sufficient; selecting the $d < l$ variables that explain a given percentage p_{PCA} of the overall variance is indeed a simple and popular approach to reduce the set of variables.

2) *Clustering*: Clustering is an unsupervised learning approach, that divides a set of N observations or exemplars into K clusters. In this work, two different clustering algorithms were adopted: K -means [54], belonging to the hard clustering family versus fuzzy c-means (FCM) [55], belonging to the soft clustering family.

The K -means algorithm [54] was selected following a comparison across several hard clustering algorithms, including K -means, K -medoids [56], and affinity propagation [57], that did not reveal any notable performance difference. This result can be explained by the fact that in the strategies introduced in Section II clustering operates on the spatial coordinates of points, and while different algorithms can lead to slightly different allocation of points to clusters, in no case this leads to the presence of outliers assigned to the wrong cluster, that might lead to different positioning accuracy. As a result, for the sake of space, only K -means was used in [38] and in the present work. K -means adopts an iterative approach to divide exemplars in K clusters, and eventually selects a clusterhead for each cluster corresponding to the average of all exemplars in the cluster. The number K of clusters to be created is selected as part of the initialization of the algorithm, together with an initial set of clusterheads; in this work the K -means++ algorithm, proposed in [58], was adopted for determining the initial set of clusterheads.

The FCM algorithm, originally introduced by Dunn [55], is a soft clustering technique that divides a set of N exemplars into K^1 clusters. The number K of clusters is chosen as part of the initialization process, similar to K -means. However, unlike K -means, FCM allows exemplars to belong to multiple clusters

¹ The number of clusters in FCM is typically indicated with a symbol C ; in this work we decided to use K to highlight that this parameter plays the same role as K in K -means.

with varying degrees of membership. The degree of membership of a point \mathbf{p}_i to cluster j is defined as

$$u_{ij} = \frac{1}{\sum_{k=1}^K \left(\frac{\|\mathbf{p}_i - \mathbf{c}_j\|}{\|\mathbf{p}_i - \mathbf{c}_k\|} \right)^{\frac{2}{m-1}}}, \quad i = 1, \dots, N, j = 1, \dots, K \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{c}_j is the centroid of cluster j , and $m > 1$ is the fuzziness parameter controlling the degree of overlap between clusters. Higher values of m result in fuzzier clustering, while lower values approach hard clustering. The centroids \mathbf{c}_j are updated at each iteration as the weighted mean of the data points, where weights are determined by the degrees of membership as follows:

$$\mathbf{c}_j = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N u_{ij}^m \mathbf{p}_i}{\sum_{i=1}^N u_{ij}^m}, \quad j = 1, \dots, K. \quad (2)$$

The algorithm iteratively updates both the cluster centers and the degrees of membership to minimize the following objective function:

$$J_m = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^K u_{ij}^m \|\mathbf{p}_i - \mathbf{c}_j\|^2 \quad (3)$$

with iterations carried out until convergence, defined as a lower threshold to be met for the variation in u_{ij} or \mathbf{c}_j between iterations.

B. ML Algorithms

1) *WkNN*: The WkNN algorithm [23] is the most popular algorithm for range-free positioning, thanks to its simplicity and good performance; the algorithm requires no model training, and is thus characterized by an online phase only. Let N be the total number of considered RPs in the positioning system, with \mathbf{s}_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, N$) being the fingerprint collected at a generic i th RP, and \mathbf{s}_j the fingerprint provided by a target device j . In cases where a fingerprint collected in a point only provides meaningful values for a subset of the features (*valid features*), a baseline value f_{Null} is typically associated to all other features (*empty features*).

The location estimation relies on the computation of a distance $d(i, j) = d(\mathbf{s}_i, \mathbf{s}_j)$ followed by a sorting of the RPs based on increasing distance. The first k RPs are then used to estimate the position of the target $\mathbf{p}_j = (x_j, y_j, z_j)$ as follows:

$$\hat{\mathbf{p}}_j = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^k w(n, j) \times \mathbf{p}_n}{\sum_{n=1}^k w(n, j)} \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{p}_n = (x_n, y_n, z_n)$ is the position of the n th RP out of the k selected, and $w(n, j)$ its assigned weight. Weight $w(n, j)$ can in general be defined independently from the distance metric [43], but the most common approach, as also adopted in this investigation, is to set $w(n, j) = \frac{1}{d(n, j)}$. The WkNN algorithm is thus completely defined by selecting the distance metric $d(i, j)$ and the value of k .

2) *SVM*: SVM is a classification method that operates by finding the hyper-planes in the data space that maximize the

margins between the most similar data points belonging to different classes (called, in fact, support vectors) [59].

In SVM, each data item is represented as a point in a n -dimensional space, where n is the number of features in the data, and the values for each feature in the data item determine the coordinates of the corresponding point in the space. Once the hyperplanes that guarantee the best fitting division between classes are defined using the points in the training data, corresponding to the RPs, the space is divided in K regions, and any new point is then associated to the class corresponding to the region the point belongs to. When a linear splitting hyperplane cannot be found, SVM can be extended to operate with nonlinear separation surfaces by adopting nonlinear kernels, i.e., functions that perform a transformation of points from the original space to a higher dimensional space, where a separation between classes can be found. Furthermore, although SVM was originally defined for binary classification, it can be extended to operate with $K > 2$ classes. In this work the oneVSone technique for SVM nonbinary classification, in combination with a nonlinear kernel based on a radial basis function (RBF), was adopted, following the approach proposed in [60]. Given two data points associated to values for a set of d features, and represented as two vectors \mathbf{s}_1 and \mathbf{s}_2 of length d , RBF defines their similarity as [61]

$$S(\mathbf{s}_1, \mathbf{s}_2) = e^{-\gamma \|\mathbf{s}_1 - \mathbf{s}_2\|} \quad (5)$$

where γ is a model hyperparameter typically determined by exploration.

3) *RF*: RF is an ensemble learning method that relies on the concept of bootstrap aggregating (*bagging* [62]), which combines multiple predictors trained on datasets obtained by bootstrapping (i.e., random sampling with replacement) a global dataset [63]. RF uses decision trees as predictors, and can be used for both classification and regression [64]. In this work, RF is used for classification, as detailed in Section II-C3.

In a decision tree, each internal node represents a test on a feature or attribute, each branch is the path for a particular outcome of the test in the previous node, and each leaf is an output node corresponding to a decided class label (for classification) or a numerical value (for regression); a popular algorithm to grow decision trees is the classification and regression tree [65], also adopted in this work.

4) *ANNs*: ANNs are ML models that operate by imitating the structure of the human brain [66]. They consist of a set of neurons connected to each other by edges, and typically organized in layers: an ANN includes an input layer, one or more intermediate (hidden) layers, and an output layer. Neurons in each layer receive signals on incoming edges, process them according to a nonlinear function, and emit the resulting signals on outgoing edges. The structure of an ANN is defined by the number of layers, the number of neurons for each layer, and the incoming and outgoing edges for each neuron; the learning process consists in adjusting the weights associated for each neuron to the incoming edges. Learning is typically carried out by minimizing a distance metric between predicted versus actual outputs using a training dataset.

C. Proposed Strategies

Following five different strategies were defined by combining the building blocks introduced in Sections II-A and II-B.

- 1) WkNN.
- 2) Hard clustering + SVM + WkNN.
- 3) Hard clustering + RF + WkNN.
- 4) Soft clustering + RF + WkNN.
- 5) ANN.

The first four strategies in the above-mentioned list all rely on WkNN for the positioning, while the last one moves away from WkNN and relies on ANN for position estimation. Details on each of the five strategies are provided in the following sections.

1) *Strategy I—WkNN*: This strategy applies WkNN to the entire dataset, and requires thus no training; it provides a baseline for the four other strategies. With reference to the description provided in Section II-B1, the distance $d(i, j)$ between two points i and j is the *weighted average* metric proposed in [29], defined as

$$d_{\text{wei}}(i, j) = \frac{1}{L_{i,j}} \times \sqrt{\sum_{l=1}^d (f_l^i - f_l^j)^2} \quad (6)$$

where $L_{i,j} \leq d$ is the number of valid features in common between the two points, and f_l^i and f_l^j indicate the values associated to the l th feature for i and j (using f_{Null} for empty features). Given two pairs of points characterized by the same L2 distance over all features [expressed by the summation in (6)], the pair with the higher number of valid features in common will be at a lower distance. The metric was shown to lead to performance improvement with respect to the traditional L2 metric in [29], [31].

2) *Strategy II—Hard Clustering + SVM + WkNN*: This strategy relies on an offline (training, in ML-friendly terms) phase followed by an online positioning (inference) phase. The two phases are defined as follows.

- During the offline phase hard clustering is used to partition the set of RPs in K clusters according to their geographical coordinates. The resulting set of cluster labels is then used as the set of target labels in the training of the SVM classification model, using feature values recorded at each point (and f_{Null} for empty features).
- The online phase starts with a coarse positioning step carried out by associating the data provided by the target device to the most likely cluster using the SVM model, followed by a fine positioning step within the selected cluster, performed using WkNN.

The K -means algorithm as described in Section II-A2 was adopted for clustering, with K determined during the analysis, as detailed in Section IV. The metric for WkNN in the fine positioning step was the same as for strategy I.

3) *Strategy III—Hard Clustering + RF + WkNN*: This strategy resembles the one introduced in Section II-C2, the only difference being the selected classification model. In this case RF is adopted, as described in Section II-B3. Clustering and WkNN algorithms were applied, as described for strategies I and II.

4) *Strategy IV—Soft Clustering + RF + WkNN*: This strategy moves away from the hard clustering approach in strategies II and III, adopting instead the FCM soft clustering algorithm described in Section II-A2. FCM was proposed in the past for indoor positioning, originally in combination with a simple nearest neighbor algorithm [67], and later with more sophisticated approaches that select relevant clusters during the coarse positioning step, e.g., based on the presence of a high RSS value for the same AP in common between cluster members and test point, suggesting physical proximity [45]. The proposed use of FCM in this work is described in the following. Similarly to strategies II and III, strategy IV also foresees two phases as follows.

- During the offline phase the FCM algorithm is used to associate to each RP a membership vector based on the geographical coordinates of the RPs; the centroid of each cluster is then computed according to (2), as described in Section II-A2. A RF model is then trained for each cluster label, using the selected feature values recorded at each point as input (using again f_{Null} for empty features), and the membership value as output.
- The online phase includes again two positioning steps. A coarse positioning step is first carried out in two steps defined as follows.
 - 1) A membership vector is determined for the point to be estimated, based on the recorded feature values provided by the target device; the vector is obtained by using the feature values as the inputs for a regression using each of the K RF models; the K values obtained by the regression are then normalized so to have sum equal to 1, and constitute thus a valid membership vector.
 - 2) A coarse position estimate \hat{p}_{cp} is then computed as a weighted average of the positions of the K centroids, with weights given by the components of the estimated membership vector.

The coarse position estimate is then used as the input for the fine positioning step, also comprising two steps as follows.

- 1) A subset of relevant RPs is identified, by selecting RPs that are within a distance R_{fp} from \hat{p}_{cp} , where R_{fp} is a tunable parameter determining the aggressiveness in dimension reduction.
- 2) WkNN is then applied using the subset of RPs and applying the metric defined in (6).

5) *Strategy V—ANN*: Moving from the general definition of an ANN introduced in Section II-B4, two ANN structures were adopted in this work, following an extensive exploration phase, as the configurations that led to the best positioning accuracy in each dataset. The two structures share an input layer with a number of neurons equal to the number of features d associated to each data point, multiple hidden layers with a decreasing number of neurons, and an output layer with two neurons, providing the estimated latitude and longitude based on the input set of features. Furthermore, in both structures each hidden layer is followed by a batch activation layer and a ReLU activation function layer. In both cases, training was performed using the

Adam optimizer with a piecewise learning rate schedule where the learning rate is reduced by a constant factor after a fixed period to improve convergence and with periodic validation to consistently monitor performance throughout the training process.

While details on the number of layers and the settings used during the exploration are reported in Table II, it is worth mentioning here that the structure adopted for the Oslo dataset includes a dropout layer before the output layer, that was instead not included in the structure optimized for the Rome dataset. This choice was primarily due to the disparity in dataset sizes: the Oslo dataset is larger, and benefits from the inclusion of a dropout layer to help prevent overfitting. In contrast, the Rome dataset has a smaller amount of data, and incorporating a dropout layer in this case led to suboptimal performance, as the limited data made the model more prone to underfitting.

III. DATA

The strategies introduced in Section II were evaluated on experimental data part of two datasets collected in Oslo, Norway and Rome, Italy in 2019 and 2021, respectively, also used in [29] and [31] for the analysis of positioning using WkNN. The main reason for the selection of the two cities was the presence of researchers in the team carrying out the research, as this significantly simplified the logistic aspects during data collection, enabling the execution of measurement campaigns spanning several weeks. Although it is not always possible to objectively identify differences between different environments (beyond the obvious urban/rural classification), the two cities used in this study are considered as rather different in terms of both social and environmental characteristics [68]. The datasets are available at [32] (Oslo) and [33] (Rome), while the data extracted from the two datasets used in this work are available at [69], both in raw form and in the version preprocessed as described later in this section; the repository provides in addition exhaustive metadata, including time of collection of each point and. kml files for visual representation in Google Earth. A full description of the Rome dataset, that also applies to the Oslo data as regards the data format and organization, is available in [70], while details on the subset of data used for positioning in this work were provided in [31]; a brief description of the two datasets is however presented in the following section for the sake of readability. Additional information on the preprocessing applied in this work to the Rome data is provided in Section III-B.

A. Data Description

Data in both Oslo and Rome were collected using a Rohde & Schwarz TSMA6 Mobile Network Scanner in multiple runs (measurements); in each run, collected data were associated to unique latitude-longitude pairs (points) using the built-in GPS receiver of the TSMA6. Fig. 1 presents the positions of measurement points in the two cities, collected in a set of seven runs for Oslo and six for Rome. For each point, data include values for RSSI, signal to interference and noise ratio (SINR), RSRP, and RSRQ for each combination of NB-IoT physical cell identifier (NPCI), eNodeB-ID, and operator ID detected in that

TABLE I
HYPERPARAMETERS AND SETTINGS FOR STRATEGIES I–IV

Strategy _a	Parameters	Oslo	Rome
Strategy I	k	2	2
	p_{PCA}	≥ 0.95	≥ 0.95
Strategy II	k	3	2
	K	10	10
	p_{PCA}	≥ 0.95	≥ 0.95
	γ (RBF Kernel)	1	1
	C	1	1
Strategy III	k	3	2
	K	10	10
	p_{PCA}	≥ 0.95	≥ 0.95
Strategy IV	k	3	2
	K	10	10
	p_{PCA}	≥ 0.95	≥ 0.95
	m	1.3	1.3
	R_{fp}	700 m	700 m

TABLE II
HYPERPARAMETERS AND SETTINGS FOR STRATEGY V

Dataset	Number of layers	Neurons per layer	Optimizer	Mini batch size	Max number of epochs	Dropout rate	Initial learning rate	Learning rate drop period	Learn Rate Drop Factor	Learn Rate Schedule	Validation frequency
Oslo	5	{ d , 600, 300, 150, 2}	Adam	48	60	0.2	0.01	20	0.1	piecewise	10
Rome	4	{ d , 300, 100, 2}	Adam	48	80	N/A	0.1	20	0.1	piecewise	20

point. Since the triplets $\langle \text{NPCI}, \text{eNodeB-ID}, \text{operator ID} \rangle$ are unique, each triplet, referred to in the following as *uniqueNPCI*, identifies a different feature for the purpose of this work. Throughout this work, each point is associated to a fingerprint defined as a vector of length N_f , each element of the vector containing either the value of the corresponding feature, or a reference f_{Null} value if the feature was not detected in that point. Based on the analysis in previous works [29], [31], that showed comparable performance when using RSRP, SINR, and RSRQ, and markedly worse performance when using RSSI, SINR in dB was adopted to define the value of a feature in this work. The value of f_{Null} was determined by performing an exploration in each dataset using strategy I as a reference strategy. Fig. 2 presents the results of the exploration and highlights that in both datasets the error is minimized by $f_{\text{Null}} = -25$ dB; this value was thus adopted in the performance evaluation presented in Section IV. Fig. 2 also shows the standard deviation of the positioning error, contained within 1 m for all values of f_{Null} in both datasets.

B. Additional Preprocessing on the Rome Data

A major difference in the data collection campaign in Rome with respect to Oslo was the addition of 5G-NR to the set of Radio Access Technologies being measured. While the analysis of 5G data is beyond the scope of this work (see [71] and [70] for details, the latter one also including a comparison on positioning accuracy obtained using fingerprinting based on WkNN with LTE, NB-IoT, and 5G-NR), we will focus here on the effect of this addition on the NB-IoT data collected in Rome. As discussed in [31], the additional processing load introduced by the collection of 5G samples led on occasion to a partial loss of data for NB-IoT, with some of the values of the RF

parameters not being recorded (despite the uniqueNPCI label being correctly detected and reported). In [31] the issue was addressed run by run, by introducing a linear interpolation for each uniqueNPCI, effectively treating the values collected for each uniqueNPCI in a run as a time series and allowing thus a monodimensional linear interpolation. While this approach proved to be simple and effective, it did not take advantage of the fact that the uniqueNPCI that was skipped in a run could have been recorded in one or more nearby points collected in a different run, possibly allowing an interpolation with points at shorter distance, and thus arguably closer to the original missing value, given the decreasing spatial correlation of RF features with distance.

In this work a different approach was adopted, relying on bidimensional interpolation based on WkNN and operating on the whole dataset, after merging the data from the different runs. The interpolation algorithm was defined so to aggressively use points in close range of the point under consideration (any points, up to k_{int} , within a radius R_{int}), while being more conservative in using points farther away, that are only considered if they are not too far and in sufficient number (at least k_{ext} points within a radius $R_{\text{ext}} > R_{\text{int}}$); a detailed description of the algorithm is provided in Algorithm 1. The algorithm was applied to the Rome dataset with the following settings: $R_{\text{int}} = 15$ m, $R_{\text{ext}} = 100$ m, $k_{\text{int}} = 3$, $k_{\text{ext}} = 2$. It is worth observing that similar approaches, relying on the interpolation of values collected within a given radius from the point of interest, have been proposed in the past as data augmentation preprocessing techniques [72]. In this work, however, interpolation was not used to introduce new data points, and not even to introduce features (uniqueNPCIs) in existing points where they were not originally detected. The only goal was in fact to mitigate the impact of an artifact: a radio parameter value not recorded for a uniqueNPCI that

Fig. 1. Positions of measurement points collected during the Oslo campaign (a) and Rome campaign; (b) each color represents a different run.

Fig. 2. Average positioning error as a function of f_{Null} , with error bars showing the standard deviation, using strategy I in both datasets; the Rome dataset was preprocessed, as described in Section III-B.

Algorithm 1: Bidimensional Interpolation Applied to the Rome Dataset.

- 1: Consider a generic point \mathbf{p}_{miss} for which a generic feature f_{miss} was detected but not recorded.
- 2: Consider the set of points within a radius R_{int} from \mathbf{p}_{miss} , sorting its elements in order of increasing distance from \mathbf{p}_{miss} .
- 3: Let k_1 be the number of points in this set with a valid recorded value for f_{miss} .
- 4: **if** $k_1 > 0$ **then**
- 5: Set the value for the missing feature to the weighted average of the values recorded for the same feature in the closest n points, where $n = \min\{k_{int}, k_1\}$.
- 6: **else**
- 7: Consider the set of points within radius $R_{ext} > R_{int}$ from \mathbf{p}_{miss} .
- 8: Let k_2 be the number of points in this set with a valid recorded value for f_{miss} .
- 9: **if** $k_2 \geq k_{ext}$ **then**
- 10: Set the value for the missing feature to the weighted average of the values recorded for the same feature in the closest k_{ext} points.
- 11: **else**
- 12: Set the value for the missing feature to f_{Null} .
- 13: **end if**
- 14: **end if**

was actually detected. As a consequence, the preprocessing technique introduced in this section does not fit the definition of a data augmentation technique as introduced in Section II-A, but rather of a data cleansing one.

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

A. Setup and Settings

Experiments were performed on a Apple iMac desktop computer equipped with a 10-cores M4 processor and 16GB of RAM. The analysis was carried out in MATLAB R2024b, using its Statistics and ML toolbox for the algorithms used for classification and preprocessing. The code developed for the performance evaluation is available under an open source license at [73]. For each strategy/configuration, results were evaluated over 100 runs; in each run the N_p points were randomly split in RPs/training set (70%) and test points (TPs)/test set (30%), with the exception of strategy V, where the split was 70% training, 10% validation, and 20% test. Training and testing were executed from scratch in each run: a point used for training was thus never used to test the trained model. A random split was preferred to a stratified split in chunks because the only option to divide data in chunks would be by run ID; however, due to the limited amount of data and the imperfect overlapping of data collected in different runs (see Fig. 1), this choice would affect the training and performance evaluation of some of the models. Although randomly splitting points from the same measurement between the training and test set run might pose the risk of introducing a positive bias in the model accuracy due to temporal

correlation between the two sets, a comparison between random and chunk splitting over two overlapping runs using strategy I revealed a positive bias within 7% .

B. Strategy-Specific Preprocessing

Additional data preprocessing was carried out for strategies IV and V. For both strategies spatial coordinates of points in the training set were converted from the representation in the World Geodetic System 1984 (WGS84), based on latitude/longitude pairs, to the Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM) [74]. In the case of strategy IV, this operation was carried out before the clustering step; for strategy V, before the normalization applied to both feature values and point coordinates in order to take values in $[0, 1]$ by using the min–max technique [75]. Estimated coordinates provided by the ANN model used in strategy V were then converted back from UTM to WGS84 after denormalization.

C. Key Performance Indicators

KPIs were defined in terms of the following quantitative indicators, collected during the experiments.

- 1) Mean value of positioning error e_j , measured in meters.
- 2) Standard deviation of positioning error s_j , measured in meters.
- 3) Online (inference) computation time t_j^{on} , measured in seconds.
- 4) Offline (training) computation time t_j^{off} , measured in seconds (including time required to perform PCA, when used);

where $j \in \{1, \dots, 5\}$ refers to the considered strategy.

One of the goals of this investigation was to explore tradeoffs between positioning accuracy and computational complexity; this was reflected in the definition of the following four KPIs, two related to positioning performance and two to complexity.

- 1) Accuracy $a_j = \frac{\min_j(e_j) + \epsilon}{e_j + \epsilon}$.
- 2) Precision $p_j = \frac{\min_j(s_j) + \epsilon}{s_j + \epsilon}$.
- 3) Online efficiency $e_j^{\text{on}} = \frac{\min_j(t_j^{\text{on}}) + \epsilon}{t_j^{\text{on}} + \epsilon}$.
- 4) Offline efficiency $e_j^{\text{off}} = \frac{\min_j(t_j^{\text{off}}) + \epsilon}{t_j^{\text{off}} + \epsilon}$.

The four KPIs take values in $(0, 1]$, and allow for a direct comparison between the different strategies; a small constant ϵ was introduced in the definition of the metrics to deal with cases where one of the measures is 0: this is the case for the offline computation time t_j^{off} for Strategy I when PCA is OFF.

D. Results

The analysis carried out on the Oslo dataset, originally presented in [38], was revised and extended to include the new Strategy IV introduced in this work, with results presented in Section IV-D1. The availability of a second set allowed to evaluate the impact of a mismatch between the dataset used for the hyperparameter exploration and the one actually used, with results presented in Section IV-D2, followed by a new

Fig. 3. Hyperparameter exploration for strategy I in the Oslo dataset: k versus p_{PCA} .

hyperparameter exploration on the new dataset, aiming at determining to what extent the difference in performance depends on the intrinsic characteristics of the dataset versus the lack of optimization of the models for the dataset, with results presented in Section IV-D3.

1) *Results for the Oslo Dataset:* The performance evaluation for each strategy was evaluated as a function of its most relevant hyperparameters. In the case of Strategy I the exploration focused on the combination of k and p_{PCA} ; results are presented in Fig. 3, highlighting that PCA has a negative effect on accuracy, and that the value k that minimizes the positioning error is 2.

The exploration over k was carried out following the same approach for all strategies adopting WkNN; while results are not presented due to space limitations, the optimal values of k , reported in Table III, were for all strategies ≤ 3 , in line with results reported in [29], [31], and [38]. The optimal value of k for each strategy was adopted in the exploration of the other hyperparameters. As an example, Fig. 4 presents the exploration carried out for strategy II with $k = 3$ (leading in all cases to the best combination of mean and standard deviation of the positioning error), focusing on the combined impact of K and p_{PCA} . The surface plots highlight the impact of the two preprocessing parameters on accuracy versus processing load: a more aggressive PCA (lower p_{PCA}) and a larger number of clusters both improve the online time and impair positioning accuracy, but they have opposite effect on the offline time, due to the heavier load caused by clustering and model training as K increases. Whenever two or more strategies shared the same hyperparameter, a comparison was also carried out; notable examples include p_{PCA} , shared by all strategies, and K shared by strategies II, III, and IV. The results of these two comparisons are presented and discussed in the following. Fig. 5 presents the average positioning error for the five strategies as a function of p_{PCA} ; $p_{\text{PCA}} = 1$ corresponds to no PCA, and thus $d \equiv N_f$. Results in Fig. 5 highlight that a moderate reduction of variance has a slightly negative impact on positioning error, except for strategy V, that actually benefits from the application of PCA. $p_{\text{PCA}} = 0.95$, in particular, strikes as a favourable tradeoff between accuracy and complexity thanks to the reduction of d ,

TABLE III
QUANTITATIVE INDICATORS MEASURED FOR THE FIVE PROPOSED STRATEGIES

Strategy	PCA (p_{PCA})	Offline time [s]	Online time [s]	Mean value of positioning error [m]	Standard deviation of positioning error [m]
Oslo dataset					
Strategy I	Off	N/A	1.95	15.67	21.35
	0.95	0.05	1.27	17.20	22.91
Strategy II	Off	0.30	0.21	16.51	22.61
	0.95	0.20	0.20	18.20	24.28
Strategy III	Off	0.73	0.38	16.47	22.58
	0.95	0.84	0.22	17.87	23.76
Strategy IV	Off	20.06	2.27	15.71	21.41
	0.95	23.25	1.35	17.23	22.95
Strategy V	Off	33.1	0.09	30.73	24.70
	0.95	26.74	0.04	31.52	23.57
Rome dataset - validation					
Strategy I	Off	N/A	0.81	13.12	18.67
	0.95	0.03	0.52	13.72	19.61
Strategy II	Off	0.14	0.27	14.22	19.23
	0.95	0.10	0.22	15.41	19.67
Strategy III	Off	0.36	0.23	14.14	19.00
	0.95	0.41	0.20	15.36	19.67
Strategy IV	Off	8.35	1.01	13.15	18.67
	0.95	7.60	0.56	15.90	37.50
Strategy V	Off	14.98	0.04	53.39	36.01
	0.95	11.33	0.02	69.01	50.58
Rome dataset - optimization					
Strategy I	Off	N/A	0.81	13.12	18.67
	0.95	0.03	0.52	14.50	18.87
Strategy II	Off	0.14	0.27	13.54	19.48
	0.95	0.10	0.22	14.88	20.27
Strategy III	Off	0.36	0.23	13.47	19.32
	0.95	0.41	0.20	14.80	20.21
Strategy IV	Off	7.71	1.13	13.14	18.69
	0.95	6.98	0.55	15.73	34.06
Strategy V	Off	11.60	0.06	39.19	27.98
	0.95	6.55	0.04	41.26	29.43

All values are averaged over 100 runs, each run including the offline phase (when relevant) and an online phase covering a set of 800 test points. The best performance for each indicator and each combination of strategy and PCA is highlighted in bold.

with only 102 components left out of the original $N_f = 399$, as later discussed in Section IV-D3. Fig. 5 also shows that the standard deviation of the error across runs is well within 1m for all strategies except for strategy V (2 m) and for strategy II for low values of p_{PCA} , also corresponding to the largest average error. Next, the analysis focused on the impact of the number of clusters K for strategies II–IV; Fig. 6 presents the average positioning error for the three strategies as a function of K . Results show that for strategies II and III the average error increases with K . It should be noted however that for both strategies II and III the average positioning error increase is within $\approx 5\%$ of the minimum average error for $K \leq 10$. Given the sharp decrease measured for the online time when moving from $K = 5$ to $K = 10$ (see Fig. 4 for strategy II, but a similar trend was also observed for strategy III), the latter value seems a good compromise between accuracy and load for these two strategies. Moving to strategy IV, Fig. 6 presents the positioning accuracy as a function of K for three different values of the fuzziness coefficient m , an additional hyperparameter not available in strategies II and III. Results show that strategy IV has an opposite trend compared to strategies II and III: the positioning accuracy is poor for low values of K , while it dramatically improves for $K > 5$, and then stays constant to a value lower than those obtained for strategies II and III. Such a trend can be observed for all the three values of m ,

but with different positioning accuracy: results highlight in fact that extreme values of m lead to worse accuracy. A detailed analysis of the impact of m in combination with K is presented in Fig. 7, showing the average positioning error as a function of K and m . Results show that while the value of m has an evident impact for low values of K , when the positioning error is large, the performance stabilizes as K increases, and starts slowly to increase for large values of m . Results also confirm that values of m close to 1, equivalent to a hard clustering approach, lead to a higher positioning error, suggesting that the performance improvement observed for strategy IV compared to strategies II and III is the combination of two effects: the introduction of fuzziness and the use of a set of points centered on the coarse position estimate, that prevents the large errors typically observed in hard clustering schemes for points falling at the boundary between two clusters. The impact of the R_{fp} hyperparameter for strategy IV was also explored, but its impact was found to be similar to an ON–OFF switch: if R_{fp} is too small, there is a not negligible probability that no RPs will fall within the area it defines centered on the coarse position estimation, and the fine estimation step will fail. Beyond this threshold value, the impact on accuracy is limited while complexity increases. The fail probability for a given value of R_{fp} will be larger when the spatial distribution of the RPs is irregular and presents holes, as often happens in outdoor data collection campaigns due to

Fig. 4. Hyperparameter exploration for strategy II in the Oslo dataset: K versus p_{PCA} . The analysis was carried out for $k = 3$. (a) Average positioning error. (b) Standard deviation of positioning error. (c) Offline time. (d) Online time.

Fig. 5. Average positioning error for all strategies as a function of the percentage p_{PCA} of variance preserved during the PCA preprocessing, with error bars showing the standard deviation; all the remaining hyperparameters were set to the values reported in Tables I and II.

Fig. 6. Average positioning error for strategies II, III, and IV for three different values of m , as a function of the number of clusters K with error bars showing the standard deviation; no PCA was applied, while all the remaining hyperparameters were set to the values reported in Tables I and II.

Fig. 7. Hyperparameter exploration for strategy IV in the Oslo dataset: K versus m . The analysis was carried out for $k = 2$, $p_{PCA} = 1$, $R_{fp} = 700$ m.

street topology. This is the case for both datasets, presenting large areas with no measurements, as shown in Fig. 1. Based on this observation, the value R_{fp} was set to a value just above the threshold, determined heuristically.

Following the selection of the reference values for all hyperparameters, the four quantitative indicators introduced in Section IV-C were measured; results are reported in the “Oslo” section of Table III. Focusing first on strategies I–III, results indicate that strategy I leads to the best accuracy, while strategies II and III both lead to a positioning error higher by 1 m. The strategies show however an opposite behavior in terms of online time: Strategies II and III are characterized by an online time an order of magnitude lower than strategy I, thanks to the lower number of points used in $WkNN$ and despite the introduction of the classification step based on SVM and RF, respectively. The online time improvement comes at the price of an increase in the mean value and standard deviation of the positioning error, as previously mentioned, and of the introduction of offline training.

Looking at the impact of PCA, a preliminary caveat is required. The effect of PCA is to reduce the number of features, and thus the number of elements considered in the Euclidean distance computed in $WkNN$ between the vector associated to a TP and each row of the matrix associated to the RPs. The implementation of the Euclidean distance computation provided by MATLAB is characterized however by a high efficiency thanks to the vectorization of the computation, leading to a low impact of the number of vector elements in the computation time; all experiments were thus repeated with and without vectorization in order to properly assess the impact of PCA on complexity. The analysis revealed that vectorization altered the ratio between the online time without and with PCA mostly in strategy I, due the predominant impact of $WkNN$: the online time reduction was about 30% without vectorization, versus 2% with vectorization. For the other strategies the online time is dominated by the classification step, and the overall reduction related to the $WkNN$ step is less relevant even without vectorization, below 3% (this observation also applies to strategy IV, discussed later). We decided to report in Table III the results without vectorization,

to highlight the potential complexity reduction in a platform not providing vectorization; the same approach was used in the results presented later for the Rome dataset.²

Strategy IV leads to a notably different tradeoff with respect to strategies II and III; it is in fact characterized by a better accuracy, on par with strategy I, at the price of a far worse performance in terms of offline and online execution time. While for the offline time this was an expected outcome, given the introduction of the clustering and classifiers’ training steps, the worse performance in terms of online time completely defies the effort of reducing the complexity, despite the adoption of $WkNN$ on sets of points smaller than in the case of Strategy I. This apparently counterintuitive result can be explained as the combination of two effects as follows.

- The online phase of strategy IV includes a coarse position estimation that relies on the prediction of a feature by K independent RF models. A detailed analysis revealed that the coarse positioning phase may take up to the 30% of the total online time (and the ratio may increase up to 60% if vector optimization is adopted for the Euclidean distance computation in $WkNN$, as discussed before).
- The most intuitive implementation of the fine positioning step would rely on the extraction from the dataset of the subset of points that fall within R_{fp} meters from the coarse position of each test point, to be placed in a smaller data structure passed then to $WkNN$. Unfortunately this approach proved to be extremely inefficient in MATLAB, and was thus abandoned. The approach eventually selected was to preserve the whole data structure and simply set to its maximum value the distance from the TP in the feature space for RPs that should not be considered. This approach tricks $WkNN$ into never selecting such RPs, effectively restricting the fine positioning step to the eligible points. While more efficient than the dynamic generation of the subset, this approach still requires to compute the distances of each TP from all the RPs, exactly as in strategy I, leading to no reduction in complexity due to this implementation issue.

The two effects are highlighted in Fig. 8, showing the time required to complete the coarse positioning step and the fine positioning step versus the total online time as a function of K for strategy IV; results confirm that the time required for the coarse positioning step increases with K .

Fig. 8 also reports the average online time measured for strategy I, highlighting that it is extremely close to the time required for the fine positioning step for strategy IV. As a reference, the average number of points in the subset selected with the considered R_{fp} value is approximately half of the total points in the dataset, but the corresponding reduction in complexity is lost due to the suboptimal implementation.

Finally, strategy V, based on the use the ANN, shows a markedly different behavior. The online time is reduced by

² The impact of vector optimization should however be taken into account when deciding whether to perform dimensionality reduction in the feature space, since the time required for additional preprocessing might exceed the time saved by operating on a lower number of features.

Fig. 8. Comparison between time required to complete the coarse positioning step, fine positioning step and total online time as a function of K for strategy IV versus the average online time for strategy I; error bars show the standard deviation. The analysis was carried out for $k = 2$, $p_{PCA} = 1$, $R_{fp} = 700$ m, $m = 1.3$.

Fig. 9. Comparison between strategies using the KPIs defined in Section IV-C.

almost two orders of magnitude compared to strategy I, at the price of a much longer offline training time and a larger increase in both mean value and standard deviation of positioning error. The above-mentioned observations are summarized graphically in Fig. 9, that presents a radar chart comparing the five strategies with respect to the KPIs defined in Section IV-C, computed by using for each strategy the configuration defined in Tables I and II. Fig. 9 highlights that there is no optimal solution according to the definition of Pareto-optimality: the strategy to be selected will thus depend on the desired tradeoff between accuracy and complexity. It is worth observing, however, that strategy V leads to a dramatic gain in online efficiency at the price of a moderate loss in terms of positioning accuracy and precision, and is thus a promising approach. The choice will furthermore depend on

Fig. 10. Number of preserved features in the Oslo and Rome datasets as a function of the percentage of variance preserved during the PCA preprocessing p_{PCA} .

the amount of available training data, as will be shown in the next sections.

2) *Validation on the Rome Dataset:* The results presented in the previous section were obtained after a thorough exploration of the hyperparameter space for each of the five strategies, and can arguably be considered the best achievable performance for each of them, at least on the Oslo dataset. It is however worth investigating whether the hyperparameter settings determined after such a time intensive effort can be applied on a different dataset, and to what extent this will affect the performance of the different strategies. To answer this question, the strategies were applied to the Rome dataset in the exact same configuration adopted for the Oslo dataset; the corresponding results are presented in the “Rome—validation” section of Table III. Table III shows that all strategies achieve a better performance in terms of both offline and online execution time, as expected due to the smaller size of the Rome dataset. Moving to the positioning error, strategies I–IV achieve a performance in line or even better than the one observed on the Oslo data; the opposite is true for strategy V, suggesting that the higher complexity of this strategy in terms of the number of hyperparameters and architecture may lead to a larger penalty when not optimized for the specific environment of application.

3) *Optimization for Rome Data:* The results presented in Section IV-D2 highlighted that at least some of the proposed strategies pay a penalty in terms of positioning error and variance. In the case of strategy V, in particular, the ANN architecture proposed and optimized for the Oslo dataset led to a markedly lower accuracy when applied to the Rome data, with an average error well over 50 m; this result can be at least partially explained by the characteristics of the dataset. As highlighted in Section III-A, the Rome dataset is in fact smaller in size compared to the Oslo dataset, and contains furthermore 237 features versus the 299 detected in Oslo. The gap in the number of features also persists after applying PCA, as shown in Fig. 10, presenting for each dataset the remaining number of features after the application of PCA, as a function of the percentage p_{PCA} of variance being preserved. An additional exploration was

thus carried out in order to determine whether the performance gap observed for strategy V could be reduced or eliminated, and more in general whether a new optimization over the Rome dataset could significantly affect the performance of any strategy. In the case of strategy V, after a thorough exploration, a shallower ANN architecture was adopted for the Rome dataset, with details reported in Table II. Results for this configuration are reported in the last section of Table III, and show a marked improvement for both the average value and the standard deviation of the positioning error, that compensates almost completely the performance loss observed when moving from the Oslo to the Rome dataset. Overall, however, a worse performance in terms of KPIs related to accuracy and precision is observed compared to the results on the Oslo dataset. This confirms that strategy V is more sensitive to variations in size and characteristics of the dataset, and while this is a negative factor when small datasets are used, it also hints to the fact that in a larger dataset this strategy could take better advantage of the additional data than the other strategies. The new optimization did not in fact affect significantly strategies II–IV, with only a minor difference in the value of k , that slightly improved their performance compared to the validation configuration.

V. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Five ML-based strategies for range-free positioning in NB-IoT networks were introduced. Four strategies relied on $WkNN$, either directly or in combination with clustering and classification to reduce the computational complexity, while the fifth one used an ANN. The strategies were evaluated on experimental data collected in commercial NB-IoT networks, in two different measurement campaigns, going beyond previous investigations that mostly relied on simulations. Results highlight that different strategies hit different tradeoffs, ranging from high accuracy/high complexity for straight $WkNN$ to medium accuracy/very low complexity for ANN; intermediate tradeoffs can be achieved by combining $WkNN$ with preprocessing techniques that reduce its complexity. The four strategies relying on $WkNN$ are characterized by comparable accuracy across both datasets, suggesting that $WkNN$ is characterized by a high generalization capability, since it is robust to variations in the characteristics of the environment without the need for major adjustments for its hyperparameters; this observation does not hold for strategy V, which required an environment-specific optimization. $WkNN$ -based strategies are also characterized by a better explainability, due to the use of a distance metric that clearly correlates the RF feature (SINR) to the set of selected RPs; results obtained using the ANN-based strategy are not as straightforward to interpret. The explainability of strategy V might be improved by carrying out a feature importance analysis, trying to understand whether a subset of the features (e.g., the uniquePCIs characterized by the largest RF values) might drive the position estimation decisions. Future research will indeed focus on a deeper analysis of the potential role of ANNs in range-free positioning in 3GPP networks. Two avenues of investigation have been identified in this respect in addition to the feature importance analysis mentioned previously. First,

the adoption of an ANN in place of the multiple RF models used in the coarse positioning step of strategy IV will be studied, in order to address the online complexity issue identified for the strategy. Second, the positioning capabilities of an ANN will be tested on larger amount of data, taking advantage of a recently released, much larger dataset containing data for NB-IoT, 4G, and 5G radio access technologies [34]. A preliminary analysis presented in [38] highlighted in fact that the performance of the ANN-based strategy is heavily depending on the amount and characteristics of the training data, suggesting that a richer dataset could allow to close the gap in accuracy between this strategy and the $WkNN$ -based ones. The availability of a larger amount of data will also allow to investigate the impact of variability in radio parameters, by computing their distribution and assessing whether different unique PCIs show different statistical properties. In addition, the dataset in [34] was appositely built to provide multiple measurement runs over the same path, allowing to adopt a stratified splitting of data by campaign, and thus avoiding any risk of information leakage, as discussed in Section III-A.

An additional line of research will address the issue of reducing the efforts for data collection, exploring the use of pretrained models and more in general of transfer learning. While so far the use of pretrained models for fingerprinting-based positioning was only minimally investigated [76], transfer learning was applied to WiFi fingerprinting [77], [78] and recently to 5G positioning [79], with promising results.

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